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Recepcja mitu o Perseuszu w literaturze i kulturze popularnej
na wybranych przykładach

The reception of the Perseus myth in popular literature and culture
on selected examples

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Research Unit, Faculty of Polish and
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Poznań 2022

Table of Contents

1. Importance of Ancient Heroes in Greek and Roman culture	5
1.1. Reception studies – short methodological introduction.....	6
1.2. Heroes and Gods in Greek and Roman culture.....	8
2. The Perseus Myth in Ancient Literature	12
2.1. Greek and Roman Sources of Perseus Myth	12
2.2. The Most Important Topics of the Myth of Perseus	13
3. The Reception of Perseus Myth in Popular Culture	21
3.1. Children’s and Young Adult Literature	23
3.2. Hollywood movies	26
3.3. Video Games.....	28
Conclusion.....	32
Bibliography	34

Abstract

Perseus as one of the many sons of Zeus is well known as one of the brave heroes with his supernatural adventures and for his valour and his heroic wars with Medusa. In this dissertation, we briefly discuss the story of Perseus from birth, personal and family issues, famous wars and sagas and returning home. We try to discuss how Perseus changed the nature of the world. Also, based on the works of Homer and the epics of various myths. We track the media and literature to evaluate the reception of Perseus stories and epics in pop culture.

Abstrakt

Perseusz to jeden z wielu synów Zeusa, odważny heros dysponujący nadprzyrodzonymi mocami, znany ze swojego bohaterstwa i pojedynku z Meduzą. W tej pracy krótko omawiam historię Perseusza, poczynając od urodzenia, poprzez sprawy osobiste i rodzinne, słynne wojny i sagi oraz powrót do domu. Śledząc źródła antyczne, staram się przeanalizować, jak mit o Perseuszu zmienił naturę świata, a następnie zbadać media i literaturę, aby ocenić odbiór opowieści i eposów o Perseuszu w popkulturze.

1. Importance of Ancient Heroes in Greek and Roman culture

Mythology of ancient Greek and Rome originated from the distant past, their most important features of gods and heroes such as extraordinary strength, courage and wisdom were always considered and patterned by the ancient Greeks. Although these heroes were mortal and death included them, but in some legends, they were resurrected after death and continued to live to raise questions and defend their divinity, merits and virtue.¹

Myths tried to connect humans with gods, they also had important mission, as they always raised questions about the creation of the world and life after death either as the main role of gods as prosecutors or to provide information for the mortals, they conquered fear as they fought against dangerous monsters with faith, and they created security for the society.² The characters in the Greek and Roman Mythology were already known to the audience and can be tracked to earlier times.

Also, Roman mythology which addressed legends that discussed the creation of the world and Rome were influenced by Greek mythology. Greek gods and goddesses also had a great impact on the expansion of the beliefs of Roman gods, and Greek culture found its way to Rome.³

The ancient Romans and Greeks had rich myths, as Roman writers such as Ovid in several works with mythological themes such as (*Fasti* and *Metamorphoses*) recorded enduring characters and characteristics and the Greek writer, Homer in (*Iliad* and *Odyssey*) and Hesiod in (*Theogony*) were very rich in creating works of Greek mythology, they took these myths from oral literature. They started and eventual wrote and passed down Greek and Roman values through mythology for generation.⁴

Just as modern thought originated from the stories and values of ancient mythology, they have had a great impact on contemporary culture, art and literature and have taken root in modern life.

¹ S. Barber, *What does Aeneas learn from his journey to the underworld and how does he learn it*, Accessed: Sep. 02, 2022. [Online]. Available: https://www.academia.edu/36347825/What_does_Aeneas_learn_from_his_journey_to_the_underworld_and_how_does_he_learn_it

² <https://egyptian-history.com/blogs/egyptian-gods/egyptian-gods>

³ *Roman Mythology - World History Encyclopedia*, https://www.worldhistory.org/Roman_Mythology/ (accessed Sep. 02, 2022).

⁴ <https://www.scribd.com/book/518564240/The-Mythology-of-Ancient-Greece-and-Rome-Legends-Retold-Original-Ancient-Mythology-Sources-Theogony-Iliad-Odyssey-Metamorphoses>

1.1. Reception studies – short methodological introduction⁵

In this thesis, I would like to elaborate on the influence of the mythology of Perseus in popular literature and culture. Perseus as the most well-known deities of ancient Greece who have been present in popular culture since the 19th century and thanks to writers and poets is ascended and visible in modern culture and civilization and in literary works. At present, a new inclination to Hellenistic signs and culture is elevated in the modern west.⁶ They seek to find their cultural roots in antiquity, that causes the growth and exaltation of human thoughts, creativity, the meaning of human life, and the growth of the culture.

Many writers and directors are forming the connection between the ancient world and modern life today when they use mythical characters or references to places in the past, bringing it to the audience's mind. In fact, by comparing, competing, and presenting movies, books, and novels they try to place and even modify common beliefs, thoughts, positions, and values of antiquity in the contemporary period. There is also an array of sources for classical mythology that one can point to the many poems written in honour of the gods of Olymp.⁷

Homer's poems (*Odyssey* and *Iliad*), which were written at different times, are the basis of the literary and artistic representation of the myths of the Olympics gods, and the other writers of Rome and Greece were influenced by them. Such as Hesiod in the 8th century, which is an important source of interpretation of classical mythology, which describes the relationship between Zeus and Olympia.

Also, Roman authors such as Virgil, who tells legends related to specific places in Rome, and Ovid another Roman poet who, with Horace and Virgil, were the important foundation of Latin poetry, Ovid's works are a collection of mythological and legendary stories that narrate from the creation of the world to the end. they are important sources of portraying classical myths in literature and art.

In fact, referring to writers who, present and stabilize valuable and important works, are important sources of study of Greek and Roman mythology.

⁵ See: *Antiquity in Popular Literature and Culture*, eds. K. Dominas, B. Trocha, and E. Wesółowska, Cambridge Scholars Publishing, 2016.

⁶ A. Liakos, *Hellenism and the making of modern Greece: time, language, space, Hellenisms. Culture, Identity, and Ethnicity from ...*, Jan. 2008, Accessed: Sep. 04, 2022. [Online]. Available: https://www.academia.edu/2346618/Hellenism_and_the_making_of_modern_Greece_time_language_space

⁷ *Poetry and the Gods by H. P. Lovecraft and Anna Helen Crofts*, <https://www.hplovecraft.com/writings/texts/fiction/pg.aspx> (accessed Sep. 02, 2022); *Gods and mortals: modern poems on classical myths*, Choice Reviews Online, vol. 38, no. 10, p. 38, 2001.

The acceptance of ancient heritage is one of the important debates in contemporary classical studies⁸, which emphasizes the role of myths as one of the basic foundations of society's culture that leads to cultural enrichment in all periods.

Also, the achievements of reception studies were to establish a relationship and get rid of confusion between modern and ancient, which led to the understanding of classical materials.⁹

It is a part of modern human life transferred from the tradition and civilization of the ancient world, which has had a great impact on today's life by combining two ancient and contemporary cultures.

Readers are looking for the charms and creativity of antiquity, so the writers are trying to make the charms of that time more tangible for contemporary readers and show them alive, therefore, they use characters that create an image in the mind of the reader and add to the knowledge of contemporary literature by linking myth and new machine life. They also try to highlight the knowledge in the life of the modern world, for example by showing the role of fighters on the battlefield, special rituals and ceremonies of that time, and motifs. They are messages that remind us that ancient heritage has a special place in us and in our lives today and has become part of our identity. And that teaches us lessons to remember all those values by thinking about the past.

The writers with stories of strange lands, architecture, and references to reader's mind, to find between the contemporary and ancient world. The reader understands that past events are still present in life, repeated not lost, but passed down from generation to generation.

In fact, in order to show the events that happened in the past and can still be understood, they try to link the past to the present and future, in this way finding a suitable way to understand culture, historical continuity and civilizations in ancient cities, try to increase readers' understanding of antiquity and direct their imagination in the direction.

As today's reader searches for mythological beliefs in the majority of legends, poems and stories, which leads to the connection between the contemporary and ancient worlds. The readers searching mind creates many questions, and always looks for the connection between them and today's modern life.

⁸ F. Macmillan, *Intellectual Property and Cultural Heritage: Towards Interdisciplinarity*, in *Handbook of Intellectual Property Research: Lenses, Methods, and Perspectives*, I. Calboli and M. L. Montagnani, Eds. Oxford University Press, 2021, p. 0. doi: 10.1093/oso/9780198826743.003.0022.

⁹ *Reception — a new humanism? Receptivity, pedagogy, the transhistorical*, *Classical Receptions Journal*, Oxford Academic. <https://academic.oup.com/crj/article/5/2/169/583012> (accessed Sep. 04, 2022).

As many writers and poets have preserved for us the epic cycle of ancient Greek which are the basis of our knowledge of classical myths, the Roman poet Virgil in his various stories such as (the story of Hercules in Rome) or with (the myth of the hero Aeneas in the epic *Aeneid*), or Herodotus, who was an ancient Greek historian with his travels insight and outside the Greek world, who recorded the traditional stories, they created an important connection between the ancient and modern worlds that the searching mind of today's reader lead to understands the and accepts of these facts.

1.2. Heroes and Gods in Greek and Roman culture

Gods in Greek mythology

Gods are supernatural entities with supernatural powers that may not be comprehended by human senses. Mythical gods are considered guardians and powerful entities which accompany or fight with heroes. In Greek and Roman mythology, they possess powers like changing forms and power over nature. They reflect the values and traditions of society and show some aspects of the dynamics of social change in society. Also, gods are always thought of in a way that fits a culture and is understood depending on their culture and traditional context.¹⁰

Considering the gods in different cultures that are included in the structures of human life, affects the way people perceive them and the social, and cultural experience. And to understand the full dimension of the gods in different cultures, people understand each particular culture as it is experienced and described in it.

The ancient Greeks worshiped several gods, each with abilities and purposes, which influenced Greek society. They were in fact influential in everyday life, in the social memory and in their ethical views according to the poems written in the 8th and 9th centuries B.C., which led to the recognition of the gods, and we mentioned Hesiod's poems at the beginning of this article giving a description of the beginning of the world and a genealogy of the gods, in fact, makes them intermediary between both worlds and describes their relationship with each other.

Also, the Roman poet, Virgil mentioned the special characteristics of the gods in the book (*Aeneid*), which is about Aeneas¹¹ a warrior from the Trojan war, and with his

¹⁰ <https://www.thecollector.com/greek-mythology-stories-transformation/>

¹¹ <https://www.lotsofessays.com/viewpaper/2001308.html>

adventures in this book the concept of fate can be understood in Roman culture, considering that with so much connection with the gods, they were in control of his destiny.

As we know, many stories and poems were written about the character of heroes,¹² as Homer fully described them with the literary creation of the *Iliad* and *Odyssey*, the hero described by him represented the reflection of the values and virtues of the Greek society.

Although these heroes have their own characteristics, for example, Achilles, an epic hero, who played a significant role in the Trojan war, characteristics like loyalty and avenge have been mentioned about him, as he avenged the death of one of his comrades named Patroclus from the Hector and despite many risks for himself, killed him. Also, heroes like Perseus, by confronting legendary creatures, and by going beyond a normal adventure, changed the nature of the world with their own will.

Heroes in Greek mythology

The Greek philosopher, Aristotle defines the hero of the tragedy a character who “must be of high or noble character,” as well as “one who chooses to act nobly”. As a hero, it is an important part of Greek culture and its concept has a wide meaning its investigation is evident from the point of view of archaeology in Greek art and literature until the Hellenistic period. Heroes underwent dramatic changes to answer the demand of a society and to become an ideal of the time. Some heroes present a model for the future and some of them answer an urgent needs of a society.

The Greek, need heroes to better understand their special features of them that is a point in the history of Greek culture that is also reflected in today’s culture. Many questions arise in the minds of readers and viewers today, how the gods and their contributions were understood and precisely written in the Hellenistic period and how they play a role in their life today? since mythologies in the form of literary culture are the main source of our knowledge about ancient gods, and are linked to the beliefs and convictions of the human heart, In fact, myths reflect ideas from the distant past and bring culture and civilization to the present.

Also, today the human creative mind is on the one hand searching for the adventures of heroes such as Perseus and the courage of Achilles or the loyalty of Odysseus, on the other hand, visual art, animations, and epics represent the heroes of ancient Greek and make their understanding more vivid in modern culture. Also, in the study of Greek ancient

¹² <https://greektraveltellers.com/blog/30-of-the-most-famous-heroes-from-greek-mythology>

literature that emphasizes their concepts, and continues to represent heroes in popular culture.

Susan H. Edwards, Ph.D., the First Centre executive director said, “whether in ancient Greece or in modern times, heroes help define and shape the values and goals of a society”.¹³

As we know, emperors of Greece and Rome play an important role in the creation of heroic deeds and they are the roots of heroes in that era.

Heroes in the point of Greece and Rome have common and different characteristics. Just as Odysseus and Aeneas have virtues such as loyalty and courage, the other hand, we can see the difference in them, such as Odysseus who thought about himself most of the time, but Aeneas was a warrior who cared a lot about his family and city the time¹⁴, Although the heroes of ancient times reveal the values of ancient Greek, they are models that have many lessons for modern man. also, thinking about their heroic characters leads to self, knowledge, and discovering our own inner personality.

Figure 1. Perseus triofante by Antonio Canova (1801)¹⁵, Muesi Vaticani-Rome

¹³ <https://fristartmuseum.org/article/news-detail-heroes-mortals-and-myths-in-ancient-greece/>

¹⁴ <https://milnepublishing.geneseo.edu/literature-humanities-humanity/chapter/chapter-3-homer-the-odyssey-and-virgil-the-aeneid/>

¹⁵ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Perseus#/media/File:Persus-with-the-head-of-med.jpg>

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As we know, heroes can be seen in pop culture through media such as television as well as movies and books, to reach the paths that lead to enlightenment, they also help the most important issue about human understanding.

As Swiss psychologist Carl Gustav Jung in his book (*Contributions to Analytical Psychology*) defines his concept of the archetype: “We discover them to be the formulated resultants of countless experiences of our ancestors. they are, as it were, the psychic residua of numberless experience of the same type”.¹⁶

¹⁶ <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/1929-00687-000>

2. The Perseus Myth in Ancient Literature

2.1. Greek and Roman Sources of Perseus Myth

Perseus, the son of Zeus and Danae, is one of the most famous heroes of ancient Greek, and his stories show the relationships between gods, goddesses and humans in ancient Greek. Also, the story of Perseus includes relationships between heroic challenges and different adventures.

The most famous of his legends is the fight with a monster named Medusa, who was cursed by Athena and turned into a monster, and finally Perseus beheaded her. Also, his adventures in rescuing a beautiful girl -an Ethiopian queen named Andromeda- from a dangerous monster called Poseidon became famous as a brave hero and was forever placed among stars.

As classical myths appeal to the general public and various stories of them are evident in the media, interest in these myths has led to the publication of versions and translation from Greek literature that describe heroes. As by referring to the Greek and Roman sources of myths, it fulfils the needs of contemporary people by modernizing various ancient features, which have been recorded in details.

The story of Perseus is one of the most popular and oldest legends told by Greek and Roman writers before his birth and from 8th BC. Also his story with Medusa has been nurtured by the imaginations of Greek and Roman poets for centuries in different stages, for example, from the beauty to the ugliness of Medusa, the stages of Perseus and Medusa's struggle.

The most reliable early author of myth was Hesiod. Who wrote seven hundred years B.C., and the starting point of the story was Perseus, who wrote in the style of oral poets using oral stories. Hesiod deals with the origin of the gods and titans and describes Gorgons including Medusa, who was mortal and could be killed. Also, he narrated in his *Theogony* about Perseus, when Perseus separated Medusa's head from her neck, two horses came out of it. In his narrative, he described a hero who defeated the gorgon Medusa and freed her sons.

Although the most influential and famous account of Medusa comes from Ovid, Roman poet in *Metamorphosis*, she was a beautiful young woman who was raped by the sea god, cursed by the goddess Athena and turned into a monster, killed by Perseus using a reflection from his shield. Also Ovid describes Perseus in(*metamorphosis*), as a brave man

preparing to fight a monster to save a beautiful girl , the queen of Ethiopia is named Andromeda.

Also, Pindar the Greek lyric poet, started the description of myth by poet from 490 BC, he described Medusa's snake-like hair and her destruction by Perseus and Athena. Also, the myth of Perseus has provided many subjects of art and poetry since the time of Pindar. Also, Apollodorus, the Greek historian, shows another version of the concept of Perseus, and he tells a broader story because he also described details about death of Acrisius , and he also provided information about the details of Perseus's family.

The story of Perseus is summarized in the library of Apollodorus (*Bibliotheca*), a work attributed to Apollodorus which is a summary of Greek myths and legends of heroes and used myths for educational purpose and the myth writers who collected the guide books of mythology , which is collected in three books and belongs to the first or second century AD.

However, these authors present rich works from different periods and with various arts, from which the study of Greek and Roman mythology is extracted. Also, Apollodorus and Ovid are the two authors who gave a complete account of Perseus.

2.2. The Most Important Topics of the Myth of Perseus

The birth of Perseus

Perseus was a demi-god, son of Zeus (king of the gods) and Danae (the daughter of king Acrisius of Argos), one of the most famous heroes of ancient Greek, as an infant with his mother by his grandfather, called Acrisius, was thrown into the sea in a wooden chest.¹⁷ Because he was trying to have a son, so he consulted an oracle, the oracle¹³ had told Acrisius, your daughter will give birth to a son who will kill him, but he did not want to be killed ,decided to imprison his daughter underground in a small cell. At the moment, Zeus, the king of the gods, who gained the rulership of the sky with the war between Cronus and the titans, freed his brothers Hades and Poseidon and also the cyclops, and the cyclops gave him a thunderbolt as a weapon to the god of justice and wisdom, whose virtue was also thunderbolt and took it from the cyclops, looked down with an accurate x-ray and saw the princess trapped and is upset of her fate. Then Zeus as a god became a small thing with his skills and secretly entered the cell through an air vent, he wanted to make a good impression on Danae

¹⁷ <https://www.theoi.com/Heros/Perseus.html>

in the first meeting and came down from Mount Olympus with a rain of gold and filled the cell with warm and dazzling light. Also, the relationship between a god and a mortal is one of the most famous love stories in Greek mythology, after that It had been a while since they had known each other that the baby's voice came from the cell, when he Acrisius found out that his daughter gave birth to a boy, he was very afraid, on the one hand he didn't want to anger Zeus and also to keep Danae and her son with him . also, he did not want to kill them himself, so he left them to nature to die. Their story in the wooden chest in the sea is one of the most famous and fascinating legends that have inspired the imagination of many writers from ancient Greek and different stories have been told about them, as the poems written by Simonides of Ceos, the Greek lyric poet in the 6th century BC. This story was also written by Ovid and Apollodorus who lived hundred years after Ovid and told the story more simply and eloquently.

On the other hand, Zeus learned of Acrisius action and ordered the gods to bring water for them and Poseidon, the god of the sea, to calm the waves, He and his mother were rescued by a fisherman on the island of Seriphos and lived there for a long time.

Figure 2. Perseus and Danae rescued, John William Waterhouse (1849–1917)¹⁸

The Myth of Perseus and Medusa

As mentioned, Perseus and his mother Danae, after a long and winding journey which Acrisius had set for them and according to the many dangers at sea in a wooden chest, finally with the help of the gods reached to Serifos and were rescued by fisher man, on the other

¹⁸ <https://discover.hubpages.com/education/The-Story-of-Perseus-in-Greek-Mythology>

hand, the fisher man was brother of king of Seriphos (Polydeucts), since the king met Danae and fell in love with her and decided to marry with her, on the other hand, Polydeucts heard the story of Acrisius and was happy, because he could become the rule of two cities with Danae's, marriage. On the other hand he hated babies, but he knew Perseus is Zeus's son, the matter complicated. He suggested that the baby be taken to the temple of Athena, where the priests would take care of him. on the other hand, Danae and her son were thwarting Polydeuct's plans at all times and the growth of Perseus made everything easier for the Danae. Also Perseus in the temple of Athena learned many lessons about war, honouring the gods and choice of battles. After the king had a feast and asked everyone to bring him an expensive gift, and on the other hand, he knew that Perseus was not able to do it because Perseus did not have a god financial situation and will definitely be ashamed, so Polydeucts took the opportunity and asked him to bring the head of the monster Medusa as a gift one of the Gorgons. The king knew that this is not possible because Medusa is able to turn anyone who looks directly into her eyes into stone, and this will definitely happen to Perseus as well and the other hand can to get rid of Perseus, so Polydeucts sent him on this dangerous mission with a plan.

Perseus, with the help of two gods, Athena and Hermes, went to battle Medusa. He first went to the Graeae the Gorgon's sisters, who were three sisters in Greek mythology with one eye and one tooth common, who were actually the guardians of a great secret, the abode of Medusa. While they were sleeping, Perseus found them, creatures with large wings and a body covered with gold scales, as well as snake shaper hair, and took the eye and tooth from them and agreed to give them back if they helped him find where Medusa lived. Athena and Hermes told him that, which one is Medusa, because the other two sisters were immortal. Then Perseus, attached the winged sandals to his feet which he had received from Hermes and put helmet of Hades on his head, which made him invisible and receiving the unbreakable sickle from his father Zeus, he flew into the ocean and found Medusa sleeping, then he held up the shield that Athena gave him and was sure that he could only see Medusa in the shield, then cut her head and put in the special bag. Also, after killing Medusa, two legendary creatures, who were the children of Poseidon came out from Medusa's neck, the winged horse Pegasus, (it is said an immortal winged horse and one of the most famous creatures in Greek mythology), later he left the earth and came to heaven, also his brother, Chrysaor¹⁹, who was the common child of Medusa and Poseidon. after Perseus returned

¹⁹ Chrysaor was the brother of the winged horse Pegasus, often depicted as a young man, was the son of Medusa and Poseidon.

from the battle with Medusa, he presented Medusa's head to Athena, which was placed on a shield, and also gave other accessories to Hermes, the messenger of Zeus, stayed with him. The myth of Perseus and Medusa was one of the most important inspirations of many ancient artists and has maintained its artistic importance to this day. Medusa beheadings paintings and sculptures are world famous. Magic also plays an important role in the mythical story of Perseus, which was mentioned by many poets.

Figure 3. Pegasus the winged horse by Fortunino Matania (1881-1963)²⁰

Although, Medusa in late classical art, depicted with a beautiful woman, Athena transformed her into a ugly creature, but Greek writers and artists imagined her as a monster born into a family of monsters.

Also, the story of Perseus and Medusa is a story of endurance, courage and dignity. He fought for years to defend his mother's honour. He also is incredibly brave, no matter how powerful or scary the monster is. It was the help of the gods and his intelligence that made him successful.

On further examination, Athena and Medusa appear to be myth that teach women how to care for each other and to care for each other in a male dominated society where rape is a threat. Also, Medusa connection to the present is also enduring as an allegorical figure

²⁰ <https://fineartamerica.com/featured/pegasus-the-winged-horse-fortunino-matania.html>

of beauty or an image to place the face of hated woman in power, and shows that your destiny will not always be what you expect, which you will eventually face and cannot avoid or change.

Figure 4. Bronze head of Medusa by Caligula (37-41 B.C.)²¹

The Myth of Perseus and Andromeda

After returning Perseus from his journey to home (Seriphos), he passed through Ethiopia, he was traveling along the coast riding Pegasus, realized that a naked girl named Andromeda (Ethiopian princess), the beautiful daughter of Cepheus and queen Cassiopeia, chained to a big rock and a sea monster will come to devour her. Because the girl's mother, Cassiopeia, the queen of ancient Ethiopia had claimed that she is most beautiful women in the world and more beautiful than the girls of the sea Nereus. On the other hand her statement made Poseidon (the brother of Zeus and the god of sea) very angry because he created the most beautiful creatures in the form of sea nymphs and by sending the sea monster (Cetus), intended to destroy the kingdom of Cepheus and brings Ethiopia into water and makes it fall. he only regret the punishment if her daughter Andromeda is sacrificed for him. Since Perseus fell in love of Andromeda when he saw her and he offered Andromeda's parents (Cassiopeia and Cepheus) to marry her if he would save her life. He fought the monster with the powerful weapon given to him by the god Hermes and goddess Athena, and attacked the sea monster from above and by showing Medusa's head, turned the monster into stone, then plunging his sword into him as the sea filled with blood.

²¹ <https://www.worldhistory.org/image/1322/bronze-head-of-medusa/>

Then Perseus got Andromeda, he didn't accept the gift (kingdom as dowry) that Andromeda's parents had offered him. then Perseus married Andromeda in the royal hall of Cepheus, on the other hand, Phineus, who is said to be engaged with Andromeda and failed to save her from the sea monster, attacked Perseus instead. But Perseus showed them Medusa's head and turned them into stone. In the end, Perseus married Andromeda, (she later became queen of the city Mycenae that Perseus had established). And took her to his mother, but Danae who was unwilling to marry king Polydeucts, she had to hide. Then Perseus entered a party hosted by Polydeucts, he realized that Polydeucts is still oppressing people and flashed Medusa's head, the king and guests became stones.

Perseus was placed among the stars by the gods because of the power he had gained in Ethiopia. Also, there are constellation named Perseus, Cepheus and Cassiopeia. Also, Athena requested that Andromeda be placed among the stars, which is constellation and galaxy.

Although Perseus's love for Andromeda is due to her beauty and nobility, this makes Perseus attack the sea monster with his great strength and unparalleled intelligence, as well as the help of the gods, and defeat him and save Andromeda. On the other hand, the marital bond between them remains strong despite many obstacles and problems, and they live together for many years. Also, the story between Perseus and Andromeda has been discussed by writers for many years and they use this legend and arouse the imaginations of today's readers.

Figure 5. Perseus and Andromed, Charles van Loo (1735 to 1740)²².

²² https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Charles_Andr%C3%A9_van_Loo_-_Perseus_and_Andromeda_-_WGA13431.jpg

Perseus's return to Argos

Perseus, after battles like killing Medusa and freeing Andromeda from a sea monster on the way home, finally returned to Seriphos with Andromeda as his new bride, where he had to save his mother Danae from the cruel king Polydeucts, also he had to release the people of Seriphos who were suffering a lot from the king. Perseus attended a party arranged by the king with his friends and showed them Medusa's head and turned them all into stones. Then, he presented Medusa's head to Athena and decided to return to Argos with Danae and Andromeda. When he reached Argos, found that Acrisius, his grandfather, had disappeared and no one knew where he fled. Because he had heard that Perseus was returning to Argos, on the other hand, he had been told by oracle that his grandson would kill him, also he had heard that Perseus had the ability to turn others into stone, so he decided to flee to another city called Larisa.

Perseus took over the kingdom of Argos and lived there for a while with Andromeda and they also had children. After a few years, Perseus who was the creator of the discus throwing sport game, went to Larisa to participate in this game and demonstrate the discus throwing. Since Perseus was skilled at throwing the discus, he threw it with great force and hit accidentally to Acrisius in the audience and killed him.

However, there is another narration about the death of Acrisius. When he finds out that Danae and Perseus are in Seriphos, he goes there to meet and get them. After some time there, due to the death of king Polydeuct and during his funeral, by chance, due to the wind, the discus is released from Perseus's hand hits Acrisius's head and kills him.

Later, Perseus, as he was very ashamed of his grandfather's death, and he did not want to take over the kingdom of a city that killed its former king himself, so he met the twin brother of Acrisius who was called Proteus and he was the king of Tyrin. And he exchanged with them that he would leave the kingdom of Argos to him and his son Megapenthes and himself would become the king of the Tyrin region and stayed there, also, later he established the city of Mycenae and Perseus became famous for building the city of Mycenae made by cyclopes – one-eyed giants – with its strange walls held together with no materials. Finally, Perseus settled in Mycenae and lived there for many years with Andromeda and had a long and powerful reign as king there.

Figure 6. Perseus return to Argos²³

²³ <https://perseus-thehero-lp3a.weebly.com/return.html>

3. The Reception of Perseus Myth in Popular Culture

In this part of the article, we elaborate acceptance of Perseus legends in popular culture and literature as well as its impact on modern reception. As mentioned, many times in this article, Perseus is one of the first and most popular legends in ancient Greek mythology, he is one of the most important ancient figures whose unique characteristics later connected it to more and different cultures.

As Homer, in his works, has promoted Greek culture and familiarity with ancient Greek, also, he included legends about the warriors and heroes of the Trojan war in his works, which today have been transfers to pop culture in various ways.

According to the Rosie Hewlett the author of *Medusa* book: “each time these stories are told and retold, people naturally add their own spark, placing a piece of themselves into the narrative.”²⁴ Also she says, this ability to “retell but also reimagine” and this is the reason why she studies classical civilization.

Gods and heroes are used today to help explain modern life. Stories of these immortal beings help to obscure natural phenomena and explain the complex life of today. In fact, believing in gods is a way to build and maintain larger societies that project modern values on ancient culture and the result of social change. Also, by using myth, the culture and social behaviours of different ethnic groups can be analysed, because myth is a message that has passed through the centuries to form the roots of a nation’s culture and literature. Myths are closely related to the structure of literature, the role of myth in literature can be one of the important methods of literary criticism and diversity views in this field, a link to oral and written literature, as the oral literature of some of the myth, is still relevant today.

As mentioned in parts of this article, nowadays writers try to include mythology in their works²⁵, in fact, they evaluate literature from a mythological point of view. Since myth has a long history in literature and is an important part of it, and In Homer’s works, in the mythological section of the (*Iliad* and *Odyssey*), where myths have entered literature and literary myths have been created it can be understood in influencing society and within human beings. Thus, writers use myth to recreate the culture of the past, while at the same time incorporating their moral aspects into literature. The use of myths in literature emphasizes the continuity of modern beliefs and thinking.

²⁴ <https://harpymagazine.com/home-1/medusa-rosie-hewlett-myth-retelling>

²⁵ A. Ceglarska, *The role of myth in political thought*, <https://www.ejournals.eu/pliki/art/12692/>

As mentioned, the myth of Medusa was intertwined with the myth of the hero Perseus, which also helps artists in interpreting also the pictures of legendary monsters that are popular subjects²⁶, it was part of a heroic confrontation in which the hero was always won.

As the mythical monster, Medusa and her sisters with ancient origins have been shown in art and culture from ancient Greek to the present day, there are truths hidden in them that are like the symbols of a monster, a rape victim that continue to be recreated in popular culture, and experiences that are still palpable in the modern world. The concepts that were as prominent then as they now teach a lot about how people look at life today.

As mentioned, Perseus went through many obstacles from fighting Medusa to rescuing Andromeda from the sea monster, however, he died with a happy ending²⁷ and because of the action he took, he left aspects like bravery and heroism among the Greeks. Even today, his lessons are used in human life and are being modernized.

Just as the ancient writers record the facts and mythical characters, today historians and researchers are engaged in archaeological explorations and studies in the field of mythology²⁸ to achieve more accurate results and find more detail, who today play an important role in interpretations and discussions, who still see the basis and culture of ancient Greek in the civilization of today's societies.

Also, Simon Young, a British historian of popular culture and one of the editors and authors of the magic book say, the mythical creatures found in folklore do different things. Young says:

they uphold morality, enforce taboos, and connect to divinity. Warn against dangers and, most importantly, entertain". Young says," If had to sum it up, though, I'd say they teach us modesty. There are things that are bigger than us that we glimpsed and things that we cannot even conceive: Things that are, in any case, beyond our control. They are the unknown. The darkness under the stairs or off the part in the forest or in our neighbour's heart.²⁹

Although Medusa is a creature that is widely known in Greek mythology. It is mostly known for being a monster, but also for its destructive action and influence in today's world, and today it stands as an allegorical figure of beauty or an image to place the face of a hated woman in power. She has offered Perseus the ability to defeat all his enemies by turning

²⁶ https://www.metmuseum.org/toah/hd/medu/hd_medu.htm

²⁷ <https://ofthestarsandthestories.wordpress.com/2017/08/14/the-hero-from-greece-with-a-happy-ending/>

²⁸ J. M. Levi, *Myth and History Reconsidered: Archaeological Implications of Tzotzil-Maya Mythology*, *American Antiquity*, vol. 53, no. 3, pp. 605–619, 1988, doi: 10.2307/281221.

²⁹ *A brief history of the world's most storied mythical creatures*, *Mythical creatures*, The Guardian, <https://www.theguardian.com/mythical-creatures/ng-interactive/2019/aug/26/most-legendary-mythical-creatures-history> (accessed Aug. 22, 2022).

them into stones and also gave him the gift of Pegasus. In modern culture, it is seen as a symbol of the power of wise intelligence that a snake head like her is a symbol of cunning.

Also, says Young, “Some stories are in our earliest human records and can also be found in internet legends.”³⁰ he points out that “other stories, though, have a sell-by date and wither away. It is not the case that all stories are retooled. Each generation also creates its own narratives.”³¹

As mentioned, monsters reveal things about humans, scary alien creatures that contain myths, and help societies define cultural boundaries.

Also, in classical Greek and Roman mythology, many of these creatures are female. and ancient male writers wrote stories of female monsters, such as Roman poet, Ovid wrote about Medusa in(*Metamorphoses*)in the first, century A.D. epic.

And in Homer’s (*Odyssey*), in the seventh or eighth century B.C., Scylla is described as a six-headed and twelve-legged creature and Charybdis, as a sea of doom, both described as female³².

Also, Jess Zimmerman, a journalist which examines the monsters of antiquity through a feminist lens, raised “women have been monsters, and monsters have been women, in centuries’ worth of stories,”³³ she notes in the book, “because stories are a way to encode these expectations and pass them on.”³⁴

She also combines literary analysis with memories to consider each monster as a broad metaphor for what is expected of women today. “The traits of [monsters] represent-aspiration, knowledge, strength, desire – are not hideous” Zimmerman writes also “In men’s hands, they have always been heroic.”³⁵

3.1. Children’s and Young Adult Literature

The great novels of ancient Greek, is one of the most important works that shaped the vision of children and teenagers in understanding the nature of life in ancient Greek world. Also, the authors try to help children understand their time with the ideas and language of Greek

³⁰ A brief history of the world’s..., op. cit.

³¹ Ibidem.

³² <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Scylla-and-Charybdis>

³³ <https://www.smithsonianmag.com/arts-culture/meet-female-monsters-greek-mythology-medusa-sphinx-180977364/>

³⁴ <https://greekreporter.com/2022/03/05/greek-goddess-the-sphinx-embodied-concept-of-knowledge-as-power/>

³⁵ <https://www.smithsonianmag.com/arts-culture/meet-female-monsters-greek-mythology-medusa-sphinx-180977364/>

literature. In the books for children, which are shown through fantasy stories by explaining myths, the author tries by creating the world of ancient heroes focus on children's imagination, which are important resources and instructive lesson for them. It is also possible to investigate children's fantasy, it increases their ability to absorb information from the ancient world.

Nevertheless, it is a fascinating collection of mythological retellings in which the author finds a new way to introduce Greek mythology into the majority of fantasy stories. Also, as educational resources, it creates an opportunity for children to grasp concepts that they do not experience in their daily lives.

As Greek mythology always plays a role in the culture and art of the modern world, children of different ages receive informative messages, such as the courage that exists in the battle with monsters or the loyalty of heroes, which leads to secrets hidden in this series of stories that attract children. And directs their imaginations in a direction to seek to discover these concepts.

Also in the novel Rick Riordan's fantasy series (*Percy Jackson and the Olympians*)³⁶, American author wrote this fantasy novel and uses a character named Percy to portray Greek mythology through his collection of books, *Percy Jackson and the Olympians*. In each book of these series, heroes, monsters, gods, and goddesses all play an important role in how Rick portrays Greek mythology. He also, in his book added a young character named Percy who can discuss the resemblance to Perseus. Percy fights with the titans, led by Cronus, who want to destroy the world and make the world full of chaos by unleashing monsters and tough fights. Also Percy, who made many sacrifices to fight the titans and Cronus with his friends like Annabeth and Luke Castellan, son of Hermes and Nico Angelo, son of Hades, who joined him in this adventurous journey and tries many times to save his friends from danger, even when he knew that there was a danger of turning into stone by fighting Medusa, but with great effort he cut off Medusa's head. In this battle, he was always loyal to his friends and defended them, and he never left them in any situation, even when they told him to leave his friends and complete tasks, but he did not accept and believed that he should be loyal to his friends until the end. Also, when he has to choose between his friends and living with his mother, Percy goes with his friends and doesn't leave them, promising his mother that he will return and goes underground.

³⁶ *Percy-Jackson-and-the-Olympians*, Rick Riordan, Miramax books, 2005-2009

In this story, the issue of betrayal is also raised, since Luke a demigod who was Percy's friend at the beginning, but then with Cronus's connivance, planned to kill Percy and wanted to poison him, and at the last moment, he announced to Percy that Cronus will destroy the age of gods. Although Luke ends up killing himself with Annabeth's knife, he sacrifices himself to defeat Cronus. Percy wins and saves Olympus and gods, also he fulfills the dreams of his friends, on the other hand, he does not accept immortality from the gods and wants to remain mortal.

They were both (Perseus and Percy) demigods with a divine father and mortal mother. And killed Medusa by beheading, in different circumstances but with similar equipment, for example, Perseus was given the Zeus's sword by the gods and Percy was given his father's (Zeus) sword. Hermes gave his winged sandals to Perseus, and Hermes's son Luke gave Hermes's winged shoes to Percy.

Rick uses different creatures with different and unique characteristics in his collection stories, which are famous in Greek literature. Also, by replacing these characters in comparison with the mythological creatures of ancient Greek, he tries to portray the culture values of ancient Greek and transfers to today's modern societies and he related the archetypes to the current culture by placing them in different position.

As he presents different mythological characters, especially children, and reminds them that they can be a hero in the society by placing themselves in the position and develop their special abilities. Also, he knew that children would enjoy mythology and by presenting a different topic, he tried to attract the audience of children and teenagers. And with the fictional stories that are derived from the gods of ancient Greek and creation of magical works, he fascinates children, and because of the creation of new places and characters in his book series, he continues to interest the reader to continue the stories.

Also, in this series of books, children in addition to being faced with interesting and entertaining stories, can understand things like the loyalty that some of Percy's friend such as Grover, who met Percy at school and when he found out that Percy is a strong boy and on the other hand is a demigod, Grover accompanied him to the camp and was with Percy in the fight against the titans. also, his bravery that even with countless dangers is very clear throughout the stories. it can be mentioned Percy's forgiveness that Nico, Hades' son and one of the Percy's friends, is forgiven by Percy because he tried to betray him at the first.

Although Percy's bravery is very evident throughout the story. Considering that he is not afraid of anything and goes through all the danger to save the lives of his friends, he

bravely fights many monsters and strange creatures and finally succeeds in defeating Cronus and saved Olympus.

3.2. Hollywood movies

Hollywood directors are always eager to use fantastic and mythological characters in their works, because they want to make the audience of this movie industry fascinated by powerful characters in order to interpret the world they live in. In addition, supernatural effects, create fantastic contents and find a way to transfer a distant culture to modern human life in the filmmaking scene.

The film industry by using mythological stories and narratives , actually portrays the difference between the two modern and ancient mythological worlds, they connect the audience to distant legends and recreate ancient myths in modern human life and they appear important in the contemporary structure.

They also by creating a genre try to explain natural processes through the narrative of strange animals in the form of monsters and by portraying symbolic monsters, they make the audience wonder if these creatures are real? Also, they create a perspective that increase fear and tension and by modernizing the classic scary monster, they add to the modern horror. Also, create metaphors and allusions that can be analysed in a modern way.

As mentioned, The Greek and Roman mythology contained extraordinary characters and creatures that were ideal for cinematic adventure. For example, in a 2010 movie, Clash of titans³⁷, a film in which narrates is a fantasy adventure in which the hero Perseus plays a major role, include some of the creatures of Greek myths. Also, the movie is based on history and myth, about destroying a monster through the efforts of a hero. The director tries to draw a believable mythological world for the audience and to show the magical world in the movie by today's digital industry. Since the lives of the titans who are the parents and predecessors of the gods and before existence of mortals, their reign were ended by the gods, Zeus, the creator of mankind, named his brother Hades, the god of the underworld. After a long time, when mortals were bored with the lusts and selfish goals of the gods, on the other hand, the power of Zeus weakened and Hades – avenging god of the underworld – wanted to take revenge on Zeus, who called him the god of the underworld. He claimed that by releasing the Kraken, the sea monster against Argos would destroy mortals and the earth. Perseus, the

³⁷ <https://www.imdb.com/title/tt0800320/>

son of Zeus decides to fight Hades, the one who responsible for his numerous mortal family problems and death, also to return power to Zeus.

Hades also claimed that by presenting Andromeda to him, he will stop releasing the Kraken. Despite this, Perseus, with the help of soldiers who knew the city of Argos well, as well as monster hunters who were very skilled, also magicians who helped Perseus in this fight with their magical power, went to war with the monster. they pass many obstacles and fight against enemies like scorpions, since Perseus is a demigod and due to his divine origin he has enough powers to fight enemies, although they realize that to defeat the monster they must use Medusa's head to turn into stone, so to find Hades in the underworld, they also encounter Medusa.

After finding Medusa, two soldiers are first killed by her and Perseus is trapped in areas where Medusa cannot shoot him. After two warriors hurt Medusa, Perseus uses the shield's reflection and the sword he received from Zeus to decapitate Medusa's head from her body. Perseus by showing Medusa's head, turn the Kraken into stone and saves Andromeda, also, using the sword he received from Zeus, which contained the lightning bolt of the sword, he banished Hades to the underworld. And return the power to Zeus.

At the end, Perseus after defeating the monster and Hades, he saved Olympia from falling and solidifying the foundations of Zeus' rule, Finally, he ended the battle and returned to his human form, rides Pegasus towards Mount Olympus and says that he does not want to be one of them, and goes over the sea to Argos.

Although some combined adventures can be a timeless narrative, and attractive to young and old. However, The message of this film is about valuing humanity, wisdom and the struggle for family love. Also, the film gives you the opportunity to talk to your children about real-life issues such as family love and self, sacrifice to save others, the effects of futility and self, and centeredness on others and yourself. and logical concept that pursues different learning goals.

Also, the science fiction genre that is based on monsters and strange animals that can be scary, exciting and comical, in addition to entreating and attracting children and audiences to the film and conveying ancient ideas to their minds, and the model taking away from the hero of the film ,it also transfer the violence to the character and thoughts of audience. Also, in the film the representation of the thoughts and opinions of the filmmakers with regard to various violence with ancient symbols in the story cover, affects the norms and beliefs of the audience and their perceptions and views, which leads to the reflection and analysis to children .and it can also lead to the spread of violence in society.

It also offers a deep understanding of Greek tradition mythology, it also, includes a range of interesting and exciting lessons with vital skills, which leads to an understanding of a theme in the plot and helps to identify linguistic tools and the connection of texts with social and historical contexts.

Although the film has very violent scenes, fantasy violence, such as sword fights, eruptions and explosions, and fire monsters, and content that may bother and scare children, on the other hand, it offers ideas for talking to children that mainly attract teenagers. It also has messages for families that can empower their children to help them, cross impossible obstacles. And the lesson of self-sacrifice, where Zeus forgives Hades, and Perseus shows values such as self-sacrifice and perseverance.

Other movies with the similar subject of Greek mythology include³⁸:

- Wrath of Titans (2012)³⁹
- Hercules (1997)⁴⁰
- Troy (2004)⁴¹
- Immortals (2011)⁴²
- O Brother, Where art Thou (2000)⁴³

3.3. Video Games

A video game, it is a type of electronic entertainment that includes images, sounds and the design of subjects that are depicted by a computer program on a monitor or screen. These video games have been around the world for years and have spread with the help of the internet. Also, with the entry of large digital game companies and their related distribution stores, this industry has become very prosperous today. Also the ever-increasing access to devices that are use everywhere facilitates the condition, and the video game industry has grown with the relevance of modern video games.

³⁸ <https://www.theoi.com/articles/movies-based-on-greek-mythology/>

³⁹ <https://www.imdb.com/title/tt1646987/>

⁴⁰ <https://www.imdb.com/title/tt0119282/>

⁴¹ <https://www.imdb.com/title/tt0332452/>

⁴² <https://www.imdb.com/title/tt1253864/>

⁴³ <https://www.imdb.com/title/tt0190590/>

The most common video games are action games, which due to the fast nature and high violence of person against person or monster that provides a wide space to the players, is often a game against an enemy that is controlled by the computer and also depends on the quick decision of the player.

Another type of video games called adventure games is a genre of video games in which the player searches for secrets or solve puzzles and explores instead of physical activities, which is often designed as a solo game.

One of the best moments in the world of video games is connecting to the distant past of the mythological world and conveying feelings that are being forgotten to find their identity again. In fact, with the ideas of travel in the majority of past memories and the design of a confusing world, it is possible to recreate classic titles with a modern approach. Also, in video games based on Greek mythology, where myths play an important role, the thoughts and physical condition of a hero can be a model source for creating new characters.

Since Greek mythology entered the world of video games and recreated an extraordinary scenario that can provide a lot of information to audiences including children and adults in today's world. There are a number of Video games by performance of Medusa or similar characters.

1. The return of Medusa: Rings of Medusa II, 1991, role play game by X-Ample for Amiga PCs⁴⁴.
2. Little Medusa, 2022, is a puzzle game by Mega Cat studios⁴⁵.
3. Medusa`s labyrinth, 2016, Is a horror game by Guru games⁴⁶.
4. Medusa and her lover, 2016, shooter video game by Active gaming media⁴⁷.
5. Medusa`s heart of stone: Chapter 1, 2022 an adventure game by Tired moon studios⁴⁸.

There are also some video games featuring Perseus, namely:

1. Perseus and Andromeda, 1983 interactive fiction developed by Brian Howarths for Commodore 64 PCs⁴⁹.

⁴⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/The_Return_of_Medusa

⁴⁵ https://store.steampowered.com/app/1075830/Little_Medusa/

⁴⁶ https://store.steampowered.com/app/436110/Medusas_Labyrinth

⁴⁷ <https://playism.com/en/game/medusa-and-her-lover/>

⁴⁸ https://store.steampowered.com/app/1800920/Medusas_Heart_of_Stone_Chapter_01/

⁴⁹ [https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Perseus_and_Andromeda_\(video_game\)&oldid=1075766387](https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Perseus_and_Andromeda_(video_game)&oldid=1075766387)

2. F.E.A.R Perseus mandate, 2007, psychological horror shooting game by Gabriel Mann⁵⁰.
3. Clash of titans, 2010, Action-adventure game by Game republic, Glu mobile, Hexadrive.⁵¹

There is also a video game (Medusa) which is a two-dimensional student project⁵², whose main purpose is to convey a message about rape culture, players appear in the two main roles of Medusa and Perseus. The player who is in the role of Perseus tries to reach Medusa through difficult obstacles using weapons, that this is an important part of the game. When the player in the role of Perseus approaches Medusa's goal of defeat, it suddenly connects her memories to the past and gives the player the opportunity to think and find out why Medusa was raped and then cursed. Finally, Perseus, with great efforts and the tools at his disposal, leads him to a cave where he kills her.

Another video game that can be mentioned, Medusa and her lover, this game takes place during Medusa's journey, that his lover fully supports Medusa and wants to release him who has been cursed for many years by the wizard. On the other hand, because Medusa cannot look at her love like before, so they started this journey. Also, Medusa's powers such as turning the opponent into stone any creature that appears in front of her eyes and her snake-like hair that blocks the player's vision, hinder the progress of the game and Gaios has the ability to use his sword well.

The game can be played both for two players and for single players also. In the single player mode, the player assumes the role of both Medusa and Gaios, which consist of six parts and by passing each stage, player gain points and the game progresses.

Also play in mode co-op and include two players, VR⁵³ player is in the role of Medusa and the other player control Gaios while looking at the monitor, and both players should agree on what goals to pursue in the game.

Fighting with Medusa allows for more effort and more fun for the player to deal with confusing cases.

⁵⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/F.E.A.R._Perseus_Mandate

⁵¹ [https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Clash_of_the_Titans_\(video_game\)&oldid=1101842931](https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Clash_of_the_Titans_(video_game)&oldid=1101842931)

⁵² https://digital.wpi.edu/concern/student_works/wp988n80j?locale=en, 22346 E-project-050521-163025, Worcester polytechnic institute, 2021

⁵³ Virtual Reality

However, in these types of video games that use the female monster as a scary and strange monster, replace and studding them leads to more information about them in pop culture.

Conclusion

In this thesis we discussed some of the popular and metaphorical aspects of Perseus. As mentioned, the legend of Perseus and his heroic struggles have passed over time and reached a large audience. And the role of the gods in mythological and literary debates whose great impact on humanity is tangible.

Humans also turn to myths to answer their imaginations for their many questions which calms the mind of the seeker, just as philosophy, literature and some religious are born of myths and myths play a role through human life. As mentioned in different sections of this paper, Greek mythology is an important part of western popular culture, as they have been the basis of people's everyday ideas and thoughts. They have helped to understand the depicting the essence of nature and abstract concepts in parts such as art, culture and literature.

Since, over thousands of years, mythological elements have taken root in the questioning human mind, writers and poets have included this set of mental images in literature and art and among the most important of these works recorded in 700 years BC in Homer's poems in the two books of (Iliad and Odyssey) , as well as in the work of Hesiod (theogony), which narrated and recorded an important part of the treasures of ancient mythology and turned imaginations into reality by passing through different generations. Even today their works have excited modern audiences and there are many discussions about them.

Also, the relationship between humans and gods was replaced in the evolution of ancient human thoughts, and the anthropocentric roots in mythology and their evolutions have formed deep concepts of the modern era, as Hesiod's genealogy presents the works of gods that it describes the creation of man according to the human feelings of the gods.

This thesis presents a discussion that deals with important issues of the role and impact of ancient heroes on today's human societies.as the hero is considered as one of the main factors of history and social elements and heroism is connected with human life and deals with various issues in societies, also be found in the lives of these historical figures.

Also historical characters and heroic legends that are informed by media such as Hollywood cinema, television or video games that express the thoughts of modernity and are located in the heart of the culture and social structure of today's mankind, in popular culture influenced the thoughts of the audiences.

As it was mentioned hero Perseus who tried to save the world and people due to adventures and fights, he caused the transformation of the world, according to the developments in his path that changed his vision of the world and its phenomena by discovering the secrets of the world, provided him with the abilities to achieve his goals.

Also, Keiron Le Grice notes that “myths are expressions of the imagination, shaped by the archetypal dynamics of the psyche”.

Although, These gods and heroes have been praised and worshiped for ages, however the beauty and charm of literature has added to people’s understanding of the values and facts in the texts and the world cultural heritage.

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